

High colchicine doses are more effective in COVID-19 outpatients than nirmatrelvir/ritonavir, remdesivir, and molnupiravir

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Abstract

Colchicine has an excellent basis for being effective against COVID-19 due to its anti-inflammatory, immunomodulatory, and cardioprotective effects, as well as its role in preventing microvascular thrombosis. In addition, colchicine also has antiviral effects, an extremely favorable safety profile, and—since it does not exert any overt immunosuppressive activity—does not interfere with effective viral clearance, nor is it associated with the occurrence of secondary infections.

However, all studies to date on the effects of low-dose colchicine for COVID-19 treatment are conflicting and rather disappointing.

As colchicine has the remarkable ability to accumulate intensively in leukocytes—where the cytokine storm is generated—we initiated high but safe doses of colchicine for COVID-19 patient treatment. Our assumption was that a safe increase in colchicine dosage to reach micromolar concentrations in leukocytes would result in NLRP3 inflammasome/cytokine storm inhibition and would enhance its antiviral effect by inducing microtubule dissociation.

Outpatients' high-dose colchicine treatment practically prevents hospitalizations. Total colchicine uptake analysis demonstrates an inverse relationship with hospitalization. The duration of colchicine uptake also shows an inverse relationship with hospitalization and post-COVID-19 symptoms. Unlike the WHO-recommended antiviral preparations molnupiravir, remdesivir, and paxlovid, colchicine—in addition to its antiviral effect—prevents the cytokine storm and therefore has a strong effect not only in outpatients but also in inpatients. Unlike antivirals, colchicine significantly reduces post-COVID-19 symptoms. The side effects of colchicine are similar to those of paxlovid. The price of colchicine is incomparably lower, and it is also easily available.

Keywords

COVID-19, colchicine, colchicine doses, colchicine side effects, antiviral drugs, cytokine storm

Introduction

Successful treatment of COVID-19 outpatients is the greatest challenge. Around 80% of patients with COVID-19 were classified as mild (non- or mild pneumonia) and recovered without specific treatment. However, about 15% of patients deteriorated (severe COVID-19), and 5% were critical (Wu and McGoogan 2020). These 20% of patients required hospitalization. The key criterion for successful outpatient treatment is a reduction in hospitalizations. After millions of publications and tens of thousands of pre-clinical and/or clinical studies, more than 700 agents have been reported to exhibit anti-SARS-CoV-2 effects (Li et al. 2023). However, the World Health Organization (WHO) recommends only three antiviral drugs for outpatient use—molnupiravir (lagevrio), remdesivir (veklury), and ritonavir-boosted nirmatrelvir (paxlovid). All these drugs, which inhibit viral replication, have serious side effects, their effectiveness varies widely, and they are very expensive (Ahmed-Khan et al. 2023; Mitev 2024a; Sax 2024).

In theory, colchicine has an excellent basis for being effective against COVID-19 due to its antiviral, anti-inflammatory, and immunomodulatory effects, its prevention of microvascular thrombosis, and its cardioprotective properties (Reyes et al. 2021; Mitev 2024a; Rabbani et al. 2024). However, all studies to date on the effects of colchicine have been conducted with low doses, and the results are conflicting and rather disappointing when evaluating its efficacy in inpatients (RECOVERY Collaborative Group 2021; Elshiwiy et al. 2024; Mitev 2024a; Rabbani et al. 2024). In previous publications, we demonstrated an excellent effect of high-dose colchicine in 785 inpatients, whose mortality decreased in a dose-dependent manner—between 2- and 7-fold [Mitev et al. 2023b; Mitev 2024b; Tiholov et al. 2024]. We are now demonstrating the effect of colchicine in the treatment of outpatients while also monitoring their post-COVID-19 symptoms.

Materials and methods

The research was approved by the Medical Control Commission (MCC) of University Hospital „Aleksandrovska,“ Medical University–Sofia, with the following statement #17-3-54-2020. MCC approves the use of colchicine up to a 5 mg loading dose for the treatment of COVID-19 patients, based on literature safety data from 1947 to the present. Patients were carefully monitored for potential drug interactions and for the absence of liver and kidney damage. All patients were specifically questioned about chronic liver and kidney diseases and possible drug–drug

interactions, informed about the side effects of high doses of colchicine, and their consent was obtained.

We prepared a questionnaire for outpatients treated with high doses of colchicine during the period from October 2020 to May 2021. This period includes the two major COVID-19 waves in Bulgaria and all then-circulating SARS-CoV-2 variants, including Delta (https://ncpha.government.bg/uploads/pages/103/AnalyticalReport_COVID_19.pdf). The collected data were analyzed statistically.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis included the following:

- Summary statistic tables of baseline characteristics: age, BMI, and number of comorbidities; smoking status; and disease-specific information such as previous COVID-19 infections, subsequent COVID-19 infections despite therapy, days of prophylaxis, total number of tablets taken, and total milligrams (mg) taken;
- Chi-square analysis of proportions: proportion experiencing reinfection and proportion of patients requiring hospitalization.
- Student t-test for mean comparisons;
- Relative risk calculations;
- Sample size estimation.

All statistical calculations were conducted using MedCalc Statistical Software Version 22.0014 (2023 MedCalc Software Ltd.).

Results

Sample size estimation

Age-adjusted mortality in Bulgaria is approximately 15.5%, with estimated mortality during peak COVID-19 contagion reaching 20.2%. Thus, we aimed to capture a sufficient sample size to reflect this 4.7% difference—meaning colchicine reduced mortality to pre-COVID levels—within a 5% (Δ) margin of error and 95% confidence (type I error probability $\alpha = 0.05$, type II error $\beta = 0.20$), which resulted in a minimum sample size of 540 patients.

Baseline characteristics

A total of 547 responses were collected. Baseline characteristics of questioned patients are summarized in Tables 1, 2, with the respective number of patients with

Table 1. Baseline characteristics of included patients.

Parameter (n)	Min.	1 st Qu. 25%	Median 50%	Mean	3 rd Qu. 75%	Max.	95% CI	Stand. Dev	Variance
Age (years) (534)	20	57	65	64.57	72	95	62.83–66.31	12.49	259.9109
BMI (kg/m ²) (390)	14.53	22.49	25.25	25.56	27.76	65.74	25.06–26.05	4.956	24.5662
Days of C. intake (493)	1	7	10	13.36	20	45	12.65–14.06	7.98	63.7474
Number of tablets (492)	3	25	40	46.51	62	172	43.91–49.13	29.47	868.5608
Total mg of intake (492)	1.5	12.5	20	23.29	31	86	21.95–24.56	14.73	217.1402
Number of Comorbidities (375)	0	0	1	1.02	1	5	0.93–1.17	0.92	0.8524
Number of Post-COVID-19 symptoms Colchicine group(496)	0	0	3	3.274	5	12	3.016–3.532	2.9235	8.5469
Number of post-COVID-19 symptoms NO Colchicine group (112)	0	1	6	5.326	9	12	4.751–6.321	3.193	15.1142
Number of cigarettes per day (224)	0	10	15	13.83	20	40	12.65–15.01	8.93	79.8425

Table 2. Percent share distribution of responses to yes and no questions.

Colchicine intake	N = 547
Yes	496 (91.91%)
No	51 (7.59%)
Unknown	0 (0.0%)
Vaccination Status	N = 547
Yes	159 (29.07%)
No	382 (69.84%)
Unknown	6 (1.09%)
Have you had COVID-19 More than once?	N = 547
Yes	135 (24.68%)
No	377 (68.92%)
Unknown	35 (6.04%)
Smoking Status	N = 547
Yes	219 (40.32%)
No	321 (58.48%)
Not specified	7 (1.2%)
Hospitalizations due to COVID-19 prior to Colchicine	N = 531
Yes	145 (26.51%)
No	402 (73.49%)
Hospitalizations due to COVID-19 after Colchicine	N = 496
Yes	32 (6.05%)
No	464 (93.95%)
Not specified	0 (00.00%)
Diarrhoea related to colchicine use	N = 496
Yes	426 (86.06%)
No	70 (13.94%)
Bromhexine Inhalations during treatment	N = 442
Yes	349 (78.96%)
No	93 (21.04%)
Unknown	N = 114
Bromhexine table form intake	N = 468
Yes	149 (31.84%)
No	319 (68.16%)
Unknown	n = 79

Highlighted is the number of hospitalized patients prior to and after colchicine treatment.

available data as well as missing data. The majority of patients completed the sections on demographics and duration of colchicine use, as well as post-COVID-19 symptoms. Most patients were elderly, with slightly elevated BMI but a low number of comorbidities. The mean duration of prophylactic colchicine intake was 46 days. Vaccination coverage was reported at 29.07%, which seems consistent with official data from Bulgaria, as well

as the reported percentage of smokers (40.32%). The age distribution histogram of responders (Fig. 1) indicates a heterogeneous mix of interviewees, which may serve as an indicator of minimized bias.

Figure 1. Age distribution histogram of responders.

The analysis shows a decrease of 2.052 in post-COVID-19 symptoms per patient ($p < 0.001$).

Relative risk calculations show that there is a significant reduction in hospitalizations. The relative risk reduction in the treatment group was 76.38% compared to the control, with an absolute risk reduction of 20.86% in the entire population.

Relative risk -	0.2434
95% CI	0.1693 to 0.3499
z statistic	7.630
Significance level	$P < 0.0001$

Odds ratio calculations show similar significant reductions in the hospitalization rate of 80.88%, conclusively demonstrating that the subsequent hospitalization rate is reduced in the active treatment group.

Odds ratio	0.1912
95% CI	0.1275 to 0.2868
z statistic	7.998
Significance level	$P < 0.0001$

The analysis shows a significant (approximately 4-fold) decrease in hospitalizations due to the administration of high-dose colchicine in outpatients. The decrease may be even greater, as some patients reported being hospitalized not out of medical necessity but as a preventive measure during the early phase of the pandemic.

Effect of colchicine on reinfection likelihood

As mentioned in the Introduction and in previous publications, the main effect of colchicine is inhibition of the NLRP3 inflammasome after infection, which is why reinfection rates should not be affected by colchicine use. The purpose of this analysis was to confirm that no bias indicators were present and that groups were heterogeneous and randomly selected. Table 3 shows that there is no mean difference in the proportion of reinfected individuals. Because of the lack of effect of colchicine on the reinfection rate, we do not advise prophylactic colchicine administration.

Table 3. Mean reinfection rates as reported by participants and respective mean difference.

	Sample size	Mean	Std. Dev.	Variance	95% CI	Difference from No colchicine	P-value from no colchicine
No colchicine	51	34.09%	47.95	22.99	19.51–48.67	-	
Up to 10 days of colchicine Intake	276	25.00%	43.38	18.82	19.86–30.14	14.09%	P = 0.2043
Up to 20 days of colchicine Intake	153	26.80%	44.44	19.75	19.7–33.89	7.29%	P = 0.3471
Up to 30 days of colchicine Intake	55	23.64%	42.88	18.38	12.05–35.23	10.45%	P = 0.2556
Over 30 days of colchicine Intake	10	10%	31.62	10	1.01–32.62	24.09	P = 0.2043
Total with colchicine	496	25.05%	43.38	18.81	21.19–28.91	9.045	P = 0.1901

The table shows no effect of colchicine on the reinfection rates.

Effect of vaccine status on reinfection likelihood

A total of 524 responders provided information regarding reinfection rates (Table 4), with n = 23 missing data points (4.2%). According to their reported outcomes, we confirm that colchicine does not reduce the likelihood of reinfection. However, chi-square analysis revealed that a

Table 4. Chi-square 2x2 table of vaccinated vs. unvaccinated individuals treated with colchicine and reinfection likelihood.

Have you been vaccinated?	Have you had COVID-19 more than once since treatment start		
	No	Yes	Total
No	288 (77.4%)	84 (22.6%)	372 (71.00%)
Yes	101 (66.7%)	51 (33.3%)	152 (29.4%)
Total	389 (74.2%)	135 (25.8%)	524
Chi-Squared	6.231	Significance	P = 0.0126

significantly higher percentage of vaccinated individuals were reinfected (33.3% vs. 22.6%, p = 0.0126).

Effect of colchicine on hospitalizations

The hospitalization rate among responders was 25.5% for the no colchicine group and 6.05% for the entire colchicine group. The lowest hospitalization rate was observed in the group with 30 consecutive days of colchicine use. There was no significant difference observed in mean hospitalization rates within the colchicine prophylaxis group. However, hospitalization rates in each group showed a significant difference from the control group, with the respective p-values shown to the right (Table 5). No patients died.

All colchicine users were analyzed with regard to their vaccination status and its effect on hospitalizations (Table 6). No significant difference was observed in vaccine effectiveness on hospitalization. Among the 496 ambulatory patients, 31 total hospitalizations were observed—5.9% of those were unvaccinated and 6.6% vac-

inated. Among hospitalized patients, the higher percentage share was unvaccinated (70% vs. 30%). Both Tables 5, 6 indicate that colchicine lowers hospitalization rates significantly, with the benefit being more pronounced in vaccinated individuals.

Relative risk calculations

To estimate the impact and risk reduction of colchicine, three separate risk ratio analyses were conducted (Tables 7–9). The last group consisted of both patients taking colchicine for no more than 30 days and those taking it for more than 30 days, which increased the sample size from 52 to 62. According to the calculations, relative risks were 0.2283, 0.2714, and 0.1898 for the groups taking colchicine for no more than 10 days, no more than 20 days, and 30 days or more, respectively. The highest relative risk reduction (1 – RR) was observed in the third group—91.02%.

Table 5. Mean hospitalization rates reported by responders after colchicine treatment initiation.

Hospitalizations due to COVID-19 after consultation	Sample size	Mean	Std. Dev.	Variance	95% CI	Difference from No colchicine	P-value
No colchicine	51	25.5%	45.07	19.37	13.1–37.9	-	
Any intake of colchicine	496	6.05%	23.86	5.69	3.94–8.15	19.45%	P < 0.0001
Up to 10 days of colchicine	275	5.82%	23.45	5.5	3.03–8.6	19.68%	P < 0.0001
Up to 20 days of colchicine	159	6.92%	25.46	6.48	2.93–10.9	18.58%	P = 0.0007
Up to 30 days of colchicine	52	3.85%	19.42	37.71	1.56–9.25	21.65%	P = 0.0046

Table 6. Chi-square analysis of hospitalization rates among vaccinated and unvaccinated individuals post colchicine intake.

Have you been vaccinated?	Have you been hospitalized due to COVID-19?		Total
	No	Yes	
No	336 94.1% RT 72.4% CT 68.0% GT	22 5.9% RT 70.0% CT 4.3% GT	358 (72.2%)
Yes	128 93.4% RT 27.6% CT 25.95% GT	9 6.6% RT 30.0% CT 1.75% GT	139 (27.8%)
Total	465 (93.95%)	31 (6.05%)	496
Chi-Squared = 0.005 DF = 1 Significance P = 0.9453 Contingency = 0.003			

RT: % of row total; CT: % of column total; GT: % of grand total.

Table 7. Relative risk calculations for two subgroups: no colchicine vs. up to 10 days of intake.

Colchicine dose	Have you been hospitalized due to COVID-19?		Total
	No	Yes	
No colchicine	38	13	51
Up to 10 days of colchicine	259	16	275
Total	297	29	326
Relative Risk = 0.2283 95% CI = 0.1170 to 0.4452 Significance p < 0.0001			

Despite the variability of sample sizes, all confidence intervals show a relative risk ratio lower than 1, indicating that outpatient treatment with colchicine reduces hospitalization risk.

Colchicine safety

Of 496 patients, 426 confirmed the presence of diarrhea related to colchicine use (86.06%), with n = 50 (10%) missing data (Fig. 2). Light diarrhea—defined as three bowel movements per day for the duration of treatment—was reported in 242 individuals (48.79%). Moderate diarrhea, up to five bowel movements per day, was reported

Figure 2. Distribution of diarrhea and its severity among colchicine ambulatory patients.

Table 8. Relative risk calculations for two subgroups: no colchicine vs. up to 20 days of intake.

Colchicine dose	Have you been hospitalized due to COVID-19?		Total
	No	Yes	
No colchicine	38	13	51
Up to 20 days of colchicine	148	11	159
Total	186	24	210
Relative Risk = 0.2714 95% CI = 0.1297 to 0.5680 Significance p = 0.0007			

Table 9. Relative risk calculations for two subgroups: no colchicine vs. up to 30 days or more of colchicine.

Colchicine dose	Have you been hospitalized due to COVID-19?		Total
	No	Yes	
No colchicine	38	13	51
Up to 30 days of colchicine	59	3	49
Total	97	16	155
Relative Risk = 0.1898 95% CI = 0.05720 to 0.6299 Significance p = P = 0.0066			

ed in 123 individuals (24.8%), and severe diarrhea—more than five movements—was reported in only 11 individuals (2.22%).

Discussion

Our results demonstrate an 87% reduction in hospitalizations, which is consistent with the most optimistic data from the manufacturers of paxlovid and remdesivir. Table 10 clearly shows the advantages of high-dose colchicine compared to the antiviral drugs recommended by the WHO: simultaneous inhibition of viral replication and protection from hyperactivation of the NLRP3 inflammasome, strong effects not only in outpatients but also in inpatients, side effects similar to paxlovid, and incomparably low cost and availability.

We have always recommended that bromhexine be inhaled for COVID-19 disease (Mitev 2023a; Mitev et al. 2023b). Our results demonstrate the lowest rate of hospitalization precisely with the combination of high doses of colchicine plus inhaled BRH, compared to colchicine plus BRH tablets or colchicine alone.

In addition, outpatients treated under our regimen have 2 fewer post-COVID-19 symptoms.

In our sample, significantly more vaccinated individuals had a secondary encounter and subsequent infection with COVID-19. Recently, Smart and Polachek 2024 reported that vaccinated individuals are more likely to engage in “high-risk” activities, such as avoiding social distancing and engaging in more frequent public activities [Smart 2024]. Although our questionnaire did not include a specific section on frequency of outdoor or public activities, we suspect the results from the Chi-square analysis confirm this observation, since a significantly higher pro-

Table 10. Comparison between colchicine and WHO-recommended antiviral drugs: molnupiravir, remdesivir, and ritonavir/nirmatrelvir.

	Inhibition of NLRP3 inflammasome	Reduced hospitalization	Reduced inpatient mortality	Side effects	*Cost of One course of treatment USD	References
Molnupiravir (Lagevrio)	No	30%	No	Mutagenically questionable rejected by EMA	712	https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/medicines/human/withdrawn/applications/lagevrio
Remdesivir (Veklury)	No	59%–87%	Conflicting results	Anaphylaxis acute liver failure	2613	Kelleni 2021; Gottlieb et al. 2022; Ahmed-Khan et al 2023; Amirizadeh et al. 2023; Molina et al. 2024; Mozaffari et al. 2024
Ritonavir boosted Nirmatrelvir (Paxlovid)	No	26%–88,9%	No	Contraindicated with drugs that are highly dependent on CYP3A	1158	Hammond et al. 2024; Paltra et al. 2024; Sax 2024
Colchicine	Yes	76.38%	up to 7 fold	Contraindicated with drugs (Clarithromycin) that are highly dependent on CYP3A diarrhea	14	Ahern et al. 1987; Terkeltaub et al. 2010; Cronstein and Sunkureddi 2013; Kamel et al 2021; Vrachatis et al. 2021; Kow et al. 2022; Mondeshki et al. 2022; Mitev 2023a, b, c, 2024a; Bulanov et al. 2024; Lilov et al. 2024; Mondeshki and Mitev 2024; Tiholov 2024; Marinov et al. 2025

*Prices in Bulgaria.

portion had a secondary COVID-19 infection. This result highlights that better strategies of patient education are needed, particularly in the country. Although healthcare specialists are aware of the benefits of vaccines in regard to hospitalization rates, this information does not seem to translate to patients. Despite the abundance of information from institutions such as the CDC and WHO [<https://www.cdc.gov/covid/vaccines/benefits.html>], patients continue to engage in risky behavior in the face of multiple COVID mutations.

WHO recommendations for COVID-19 outpatient treatment

All three antiviral drugs recommended by the WHO were reported to be quite optimistic. Subsequent research, however, cooled the initial enthusiasm of the manufacturing companies.

The European Medicines Agency (EMA) rejected the low-potency (30% reduction in hospitalizations) and mutagenically questionable molnupiravir (lagevrio) from Merck & Co Inc. (<https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/medicines/human/withdrawnapplications/lagevrio>).

The effectiveness of remdesivir in reducing hospitalizations ranged from 87% to 59% [Gottlieb et al. 2022; Molina et al. 2024]. Remdesivir has a number of serious side effects, including anaphylaxis, acute liver failure, and death (Ahmed-Khan et al. 2023), and “this medicine is to be given only by or under the immediate supervision of your doctor” (<https://www.mayoclinic.org/drugs-supplements/remdesivir-intravenous-route/side-effects/drug20503608>).

Data on the effect of remdesivir in inpatients are highly contradictory, from no positive impact on COVID-19 mortality to some minor effect (Amirizadeh et al. 2023; Mozaffari et al. 2024).

It is not logical to expect a reduction in mortality in inpatients from antiviral agents, such as remdesivir, when COVID-19 has entered its immunological phase (usually after the 7th day), where the viral load is lower or not detectable.

The WHO’s favorite remains ritonavir-boosted nirmatrelvir (paxlovid), which is “strongly recommended in favor” (Mitev 2023a).

However, paxlovid has recently suffered a real meltdown (Mitev 2024a). The EPIC-SR RCT demonstrated no benefit from paxlovid in a vaccinated population and in unvaccinated patients without risk factors. Now the guidelines recommend paxlovid only for persons who are at high risk for disease progression (Hammond et al. 2024).

It was originally announced that there was an 88.9% reduction in the risk of hospitalization in paxlovid-treated outpatients (Hammond et al. 2024), but these percentages varied widely—from 88.9% to 26% (Paltra and Conrad 2024). In addition, paxlovid was not effective in hospitalized patients, did not reduce the risk of developing long COVID, and caused rebounds—or just did not prevent them (Sax 2024).

The failure of antivirals to prevent the COVID-19 complications is due to the fact that there is no direct link between viral replication and the hyperresponsiveness of the NLRP3 inflammasome (Kelleni 2021).

It is now clear that the hyperactivation of the NLRP3 inflammasome, leading to CS and tissue injury, is associated with lower or non-detectable viral load (Freeman and Swartz 2020; Mitev 2023a), suggesting that SARS-CoV-2 per se may not be required for continuous inflammasome activation. Disease progression in fatal cases of COVID-19 is associated with increasing inflammasome activation and decreasing viral load (de Sá et al. 2024).

However, some patients with higher viral loads died faster, with reduced inflammatory processes and increased

disseminated intravascular coagulation (de Sá et al. 2024). Inflammation and coagulation/thrombosis are closely intertwined and are key features of severe COVID-19. The aberrant activation of the NLRP3 inflammasome may also promote hyperactivation of immunothrombosis programmes (Stark and Massberg 2021).

It is worth noting that SARS-CoV-2 S protein triggered the priming and activation of the NLRP3 inflammasome, resulting in hypercoagulability–mature IL-1 β formation–which enhanced production of coagulation factors such as von Willebrand factor (vWF), factor VIII, or tissue factor, and enhanced levels of inflammatory markers including C-reactive protein, ferritin, and cytokines associated with a hypercoagulation state (Vrachatis et al. 2021).

Why colchicine is so effective for outpatient and inpatient treatment?

Similar to the antiviral drugs recommended by the WHO, colchicine also has antiviral effects. In addition, it can inhibit the NLRP3 inflammasome, preventing the hypercoagulation state and the CS. Moreover, colchicine has an extremely favorable safety profile, and–since it does not exert any overt immunosuppressive activity–it does not interfere with effective viral clearance nor is it associated with the occurrence of secondary infections (Sax 2024).

Antiviral effects of colchicine

Microtubules are long polymers of tubulin that are polarized both in their intrinsic structure. They form part of the cytoskeleton, provide structure and shape to eukaryotic cells, and serve as tracks for fast transport of cargoes, including viruses. An intact microtubule system is essential for the process of virion formation. Two key factors determine the efficiency of the virus assembly process: intracellular transport (microtubules function as tracks) and molecular interactions (de Haan and Rottier 2005).

At higher concentrations, colchicine may induce microtubule dissociation. Whereas plasma concentration after a single dose of 0.6 mg colchicine is approximately 3 nmol/L, it has been shown to accumulate in neutrophils at concentrations of 40 to 200 nmol/L–well above its K_i of 24 nmol/L for microtubule polymerization (Chappey et al. 1994). Disrupting the microtubular network through colchicine binding to free tubulin dimers may inhibit SARS-CoV-2 cell entry/endocytosis, assembly, and the exocytosis/spread of new virions. All this can affect the replication machinery within the cell, similarly to other viruses such as IAVs (influenza A viruses), flaviviruses like Zika and Dengue, and RSV (respiratory syncytial virus) (Lu et al. 2019; Hegazy et al. 2024). Colchicine has been demonstrated to decrease Dengue and Zika replication by inhibiting tubulin polymerization. Colchicine has a proven antiviral effect in RSV, where virus replication was significantly inhibited, and the levels of IL-6 and TNF- α , as well as the phosphorylation of Stat3, COX-2, and p38, were also significantly decreased (Lu et al. 2019).

In addition, molecular docking analysis of colchicine demonstrated that it targets the main SARS-CoV-2 protease (Mpro) and, to a lesser extent, the RNA-dependent RNA polymerase (RdRp), thus preventing viral replication (Kamel et al 2021; Rabbani et al. 2024).

In leukocytes, colchicine prevents microtubule polymerization and microtubule-based inflammatory cell chemotaxis, reduces their adhesion, recruitment, and activation, and leads to inhibition of vesicle transport, cytokine secretion, and generation of leukotrienes, phagocytosis, migration, and division. All these data show the great potential of colchicine against viral infections and suggest that its antiviral effect is greatly underestimated.

Colchicine inhibits the NLRP3 inflammasome in higher concentrations

NLRs (nucleotide-binding domain, leucine-rich repeat-containing), a family of receptors, form a multiprotein complex (inflammasome) together with the adaptor apoptosis-associated speck-like protein containing a caspase recruitment domain (ASC) and pro-caspase-1. As a component of the innate immune system, the inflammasome plays an important role in the recognition of danger-associated signals and induces pro-inflammatory cytokines, most notably IL-1 β and IL-18 (Rabbani et al 2024).

The NLRP3 (formerly NALP3) inflammasome is by far the most thoroughly studied NLR. It is a vital part of the innate immune system for antiviral host defense and has been detected in various cell types, including myeloid cells, lung epithelial cells, and cardiac cells (Kamel et al 2021).

The most serious complication of COVID-19 is CS, due to aberrant activation of the NLRP3 inflammasome, with subsequent vascular inflammation, endothelial dysfunction, coagulopathy, and multi-organ damage (Wang et al. 2023). SARS-CoV-2 can activate the NLRP3 inflammasome directly (through ORF8b, S, and N proteins) or indirectly (via diverse cellular signaling mechanisms) (Mitev 2023a).

Rodrigues et al. 2021 also investigated whether NLRP3 inflammasome activation correlated with disease severity and clinical outcomes. They showed positive associations of caspase-1 and/or IL-18 levels with C-reactive protein (CRP), LDH, IL-6, and ferritin (Rosrigues et al. 2021), which in turn correlated with COVID-19 severity (Velavan and Meyer 2020).

This is the rationale for repurposing colchicine—a well-known NLRP3 inflammasome inhibitor at micromolar concentrations—for the treatment of COVID-19 (Kow et al. 2022).

Colchicine has great potential to prevent the CS and the hypercoagulation state by inhibiting the aberrant activation of the NLRP3 inflammasome. Microtubules mediate the assembly of the NLRP3 inflammasome; therefore, by inhibiting microtubule assembly, colchicine disrupts NLRP3 inflammasome activation (Vitiello et al. 2021).

Thus, colchicine reduces viral load due to its antiviral effect and, by inhibiting the NLRP3 inflammasome, prevents the CS and thrombus formation.

Dosing strategies

The collapse of low-dose colchicine against COVID-19

A wide variety of scientific research, including clinical trials, on the effect of colchicine as a treatment against COVID-19 continues to this day to report conflicting results (Casey et al. 2023; Elshiwiy et al. 2024; Mitev 2024a; Rabbani et al. 2024).

The WHO does not recommend the use of colchicine but “forgets” to specify that this applies to low doses. And why does it not recommend the application of high doses of colchicine? The explanation is simple—no clinical studies have been conducted with high doses.

Of all clinical trials with colchicine, only one gave two different doses—low (1.6 mg) and high (4.8 for 6 hours)—but this was for the treatment of a gout attack. Since it is concluded that there is no difference in the effects between low and high dose of colchicine, it is appropriate to use the low dose. Thus the incidence of diarrhea will drop from 76.9% to 23% (Terkeltaub et al. 2010). Low-dose colchicine is automatically used to fight COVID-19, even though it is a different disease. It is incredible and inexplicable that despite the fact that colchicine accumulates in white blood cells, where the CS is generated, and has the capacity to inhibit the NLRP3 inflammasome, no one has repeated the 2010 low- and high-dose colchicine clinical trial (Mitev 2023a, 2024a).

Moreover, the high dose of 4.8 mg in 6 hours is even higher than our maximum loading dose of 5 mg in 24 hours. Most importantly, however, aside from the increased incidence of diarrhea, these colchicine concentrations are absolutely safe. In a number of cases, high loading doses of colchicine have been used (4 mg–6.7 mg) (Ahern et al. 1987; Terkeltaub et al. 2010; Pascart et al. 2016; Mitev 2023c). No life-threatening side effects are described, with the most common being diarrhea. Patients treated with our regimen suffered diarrhea with frequency comparable to that in the literature (Ahern et al. 1987; Terkeltaub et al. 2010).

Our dosage strategy

In the spring of 2020, we were convinced of the amazing effect of high doses of colchicine in the treatment of outpatients and inpatients. We have published some of the most characteristic and severe cases (Mondeshki 2022; Bulanov et al. 2024; Lilov et al. 2024; Mondeshki and Mitev 2024; Marinov et al. 2025). Particularly interesting are the four cases of accidental overdoses of colchicine, which led to rapid recovery of the COVID-19 patients (Mondeshki 2023; Marinov et al. 2025). Our dosage strategy is detailed in our other publications (Mondeshki et al. 2022; Mitev 2023a, c, 2024a b; Mitev et al. 2023b). In short, the NLRP3 inflammasome inhibition has been assessed at colchicine concentrations 10- to 100-fold higher than those achieved in serum (Cronstein and Sunkureddi 2013). However, colchicine has the remarkable ability to accumulate intensively in leukocytes, where the CS is generated (Terkeltaub

et al. 2010). Our assumption was that a safe increase in colchicine doses to reach micromolar concentrations in leukocytes will result in NLRP3 inflammasome/CS inhibition (Mitev 2024a).

Does colchicine have an immunosuppressive effect?

There is no conclusive opinion about the immunosuppressive effect of colchicine in the literature. Most of the publications imply that when used at standard doses, colchicine shows no immunosuppressive effect (American Society of Health-System Pharmacists 2019) and does not cause any significant risk of infection. This is a serious advantage of colchicine over glucocorticoids such as dexamethasone (Vitiello and Ferrara 2021). This is very important for the treatment of the first (viral) phase of COVID-19 infection, because the non-administration of immunosuppressants or glucocorticoids (which are well-known to increase the risk of infections) may be useful to avoid a decrease of the immune system (Conti et al. 2020).

According to others, colchicine, as an immunosuppressive drug, weakens the immune system, rendering the patient prone to pneumonia infection (Tsai et al. 2019).

Our data strongly support the opinion that colchicine does not have an immunosuppressive effect, since all unvaccinated patients treated with colchicine according to our scheme produced anti-SARS-CoV-2 antibodies.

Conclusion

Our experience with a number of severe cases of COVID-19 and high-dose colchicine led us to the following conclusions:

1. Already at the beginning of COVID-19, high doses of colchicine should be administered because of its antiviral effect and inhibition of the NLRP3 inflammasome, leading to prevention of the CS and thrombus formation.
2. Outpatients' high-dose colchicine treatment practically prevents hospitalizations.
3. Total colchicine uptake analysis demonstrates a reverse relationship with hospitalization.
4. The period of colchicine uptake analysis demonstrates a reverse relationship with hospitalization and post-COVID-19 symptomatology.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: Medical Control Commission of UMBAL "Aleksandrovskia" EAD, Sofia, Bulgaria (Protocol No. LKK-17-3-54-2020)

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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